

Studies in the Synthesis of Furochromones. Part II¹. Synthesis of Furoisoflavones

N. H. PARDANANI & K. N. TRIVEDI

Department of Chemistry, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda

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7-Hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone, prepared from 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methyl- ω -phenylacetophenone, on allylation and Claisen migration gave 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone. This on ozonolysis and cyclisation with *o*-phosphoric acid gave 6-phenyl-9-methyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran. 6-Phenyl-7,9-dimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran was prepared from 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone by the action of osmium tetroxide and PPA.

In continuation of our work on the synthesis of linear furochromones and furoflavones, we report here the synthesis of linear alkyl substituted furoisoflavones.

Condensation of 2-methyl-resorcinol with phenyl acetic acid in the presence of freshly fused zinc chloride and phosphorus oxychloride gave 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methyl- ω -phenylacetophenone(I) which was converted to 7-hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone (IIa) by refluxing it with ethyl orthoformate, pyridine and piperidine². Allylation of (IIa) with allyl bromide gave 7-allyloxy-8-methylisoflavone (IIb) which on Claisen rearrangement, by refluxing it with dimethyl aniline, furnished 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone (IIc). Ozonolysis followed by hydrogenation of (IIc) gave 7-hydroxy-6-(2'-oxo-ethyl) 8-methylisoflavone (IId), which was cyclised with *o*-phosphoric acid to give 6-phenyl-9-methyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran(IVa).

6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone (IIc) was also cyclised with conc. sulphuric acid according to the method of Shaikh and Trivedi³ to give 2,9-dimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIa), which was dehydrogenated to 2,9-dimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IVb) by refluxing it with diphenyl ether in the presence of palladium charcoal (10%).

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methyl- ω -phenylacetophenone (I) on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation with acetic anhydride and freshly fused sodium acetate gave 7-acetoxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIe), which was deacetylated with sulphuric acid (60%) to give 7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIf). Allylation of (IIf) with allyl bromide gave the corresponding allyloxy derivative (IIg), which on Claisen rearrangement gave 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIh). 6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIh) was treated with osmium tetroxide and potassium periodate to give 7-hydroxy-6-(2'-oxo-ethyl)-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIi) which on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid furnished 6-phenyl-7,9-dimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IVc).

Cyclisation of (IIIh) with conc. sulphuric acid furnished 2,7,9-trimethyl-6-phenyl-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIb), which on dehydrogenation with palladium charcoal (10%) gave 2,7,9-trimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IVd).

EXPERIMENTAL

The I.R. Spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer in nujol.

2,4-Dihydroxy-3-methyl- ω -phenylacetophenone (I): A mixture of 2-methyl resorcinol (5 g.), phenyl acetic acid (5 g.), phosphorus oxychloride (20 ml.) and freshly fused zinc chloride (10 g.) was heated on a water bath for 3 hr. It was poured into crushed ice and the separated product was filtered, washed with water and dried. The compound was extracted with hot benzene and benzene after evaporation left the residue which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 178°. Yield 4 g. (Found : C, 74.18; H, 5.98. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 74.39; H, 5.78%).

7-Hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone (IIa): To a solution of 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methyl- ω -phenyl-acetophenone (2 g) in pyridine (5 ml), ethyl orthoformate (2 ml) and piperidine (2-3 drops) were added. The reaction mixture was heated on a sand bath for 5 hr. It was poured into conc. hydrochloric acid (10 ml) containing ice pieces. The separated product was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 245°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 75.95; H, 4.61. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.19; H, 4.76%).

- a : $R = R_1 = R_2 = -H$
 b : $R = R_2 = -H$; $R_1 = -CH_2CH = CH_2$
 c : $R = R_1 = -H$; $R_2 = -CH_2CH = CH_2$
 d : $R = R_1 = -H$; $R_2 = -CH_2CHO$
 e : $R = -CH_3$; $R_1 = -COCH_3$; $R_2 = -H$
 f : $R = -CH_3$; $R_1 = R_2 = -H$
 g : $R = -CH_3$; $R_1 = -CH_2CH = CH_2$; $R_2 = -H$
 h : $R = -CH_3$; $R_1 = -H$; $R_2 = -CH_2CH = CH_2$
 i : $R = -CH_3$; $R_1 = -H$; $R_2 = -CH_2CHO$

7-Allyloxy-8-methylisoflavone (IIb): A mixture of 7-hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone (2 g), allyl bromide (1.8 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (150 ml.) on a water bath for 6 hr. The acetone was evaporated and the residue was treated with water. The product was filtered and washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 92°. Yield 1.3 g. (Found : C, 77.98; H, 5.43. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.49%).

6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone (IIc) : 7-Allyloxy-8-methylisoflavone (2 g) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (10 ml.) for 6 hr. The mixture was poured into conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml.) containing ice pieces. The product was filtered, washed with water and dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution. The solution was filtered and the filtrate on acidification gave the compound, which after filtration, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 180°. Yield 1.4 g. (Found : C, 78.28; H, 5.43. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.49%).

7-Hydroxy-6-(2'-oxo-ethyl)-8-methylisoflavone (IIId) : A solution of 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone (1 g.) in ethyl acetate (150 ml.) was cooled to 0° by keeping it in a freezing mixture. Ozonized oxygen was passed through it for 20 min. The solution was then subjected to hydrogenation in the presence of palladium charcoal (5%; 0.5 g.) for 2 hr. The catalyst was filtered and the solvent was evaporated. The residue was dissolved in benzene and the solution was run over a short column of alumina and the compound was eluted with benzene. Benzene after evaporation left the residue, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 180°. Mixed m.p. with (IIc) was depressed by 20°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 73.64; H, 4.67. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 73.40; H, 4.76%).

III

- a : R = -H
b : R = -CH₃

IV

- a : R = R₁ = -H
b : R = -CH₃; R₁ = H
c : R = -H; R₁ = -CH₃
d : R = R₁ = -CH₃

I.R. Spectrum showed the following bands : 3340 cm^{-1} (broad, chelated hydroxyl group), 1630 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $> C = O$ group) and 1610 cm^{-1} (chelated $> C = O$ group of CHO).

6-Phenyl-9-methyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IVa) : 7-Hydroxy-6-(2'-oxo-ethyl)-8-methylisoflavone (0.5 g.) was heated with *o*-phosphoric acid (8 ml.) on a water bath for 1 hr. After cooling, the reaction mixture was added into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 140°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 78.34; H, 4.16. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 78.27; H, 4.35%).

2,9-Dimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIa) : 6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methylisoflavone (1 g.) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (7 ml.) on a water bath for 15 min. The mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 164°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found : C, 78.11; H, 5.52. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.49%).

2,9-Dimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IVb) : A mixture of 2,9-dimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (0.5 g.) and palladised charcoal (10%; 0.3 g.) was refluxed with diphenyl ether (3 ml.) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and after cooling, petroleum ether was added to the filtrate. The separated product was filtered and washed several times with petroleum ether. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 174°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 78.61; H, 4.65. $C_{19}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 78.61; H, 4.82%).

7-Acetoxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIe) : A mixture of 2,4-dihydroxy-3-methyl- ω -phenylacetophenone (5 g.), acetic anhydride (15 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (10 g.) was heated in an oil bath at 180°–90° for 9 hr. After cooling, the contents were added into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered, washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 144°. Yield 4 g. (Found : C, 73.87; H, 5.00. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.01; H, 5.19%).

7-Hydroxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIf) : 7-Acetoxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (2 g.) was heated with sulphuric acid (60%; 25 ml.) on a water bath for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and the separated product was filtered. It was dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide solution and the solution was filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave the pure compound, which after filtration crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 297°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 76.80; H, 5.19. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.68; H, 5.26%).

7-Allyloxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIg) : A mixture of 7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (2 g.), allyl bromide (1.8 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (200 ml.) on a water bath for 6 hr. Working up as described earlier, the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 98°. Yield 1.5 g. (Found : C, 78.20; H, 5.83. $C_{20}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 78.43; H, 5.88%).

6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-2,3-dimethylisoflavone (IIh) : 7-Allyloxy-2,3-dimethylisoflavone (2 g.) was refluxed with dimethyl aniline (10 ml.) for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was added to conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml.) containing ice pieces and the contents were ether extracted. The ethereal layer was shaken with sodium hydroxide solution (5%; 20 ml.). The alkaline layer was separated and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The separated compound was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 186°. Yield 1.3 g. (Found : C, 78.23; H, 5.87. $C_{20}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 78.43; H, 5.88%).

7-Hydroxy-6-(2'-oxo-ethyl)-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (IIIi) : To a solution of 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (500 mg.) in ethyl acetate (150 ml.) and water (150 ml.), osmium tetroxide (50 mg.) was added. The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously. A solution of potassium periodate (2 g.) in water (200 ml.) was gradually added with stirring during the period of 2 hr. The ethyl acetate layer was separated and ethyl acetate was evaporated. The residue was dissolved in chloroform and the solution was passed over a short column of alumina. The product was eluted with chloroform. After the evaporation of chloroform the residue crystallised from benzene, m.p. 191°. Yield 300 mg. (Found : C, 74.32; H, 4.99. $C_{19}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 74.02; H, 5.19%).

I.R. Spectrum (nujol) showed the following bands : 3300 cm^{-1} (broad chelated hydroxyl group), 1630 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $> C = O$ group) and 1610 cm^{-1} (chelated $> C = O$ group of CHO).

6-Phenyl-7,9-dimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IVc) : 7-Hydroxy-6-(2'-oxo-ethyl)2,8-dimethylisoflavone (200 mg.) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (8 ml.) on a water bath for 15 min. The contents were poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered and washed with dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove uncyclised compound. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 203°. Yield 100 mg. (Found : C, 78.79; H, 4.73. $C_{19}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 78.61; H, 4.83%).

2,7,9-Trimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIIb) : 6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-2,8-dimethylisoflavone (1 g.) was triturated with conc. sulphuric acid (7 ml.) on a water bath for 15 min. Working up the reaction mixture as described earlier, the compound crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 162°. Yield 0.6 g. (Found : C, 78.50; H, 5.75. $C_{20}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 78.43; H, 5.88%).

2,7,9-Trimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IVd) : A mixture of 2,7,9-trimethyl-6-phenyl-5-oxo-5H-2,3-dihydrofuro(3,2-g)benzopyran (0.5 g.), palladised charcoal (10%; 0.3 g.) and diphenyl ether (4 ml.) was refluxed for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as described earlier and the product crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 210°. Yield 0.3 g. (Found : C, 78.86; H, 5.26. $C_{20}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.94; H, 5.26%).

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